

Chromium(VI) Dioxydichloride Complexes with Sulphur Ligands found in Coal

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CrO_2Cl_2 forms complexes with sulphur ligands having composition $\text{CrO}_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{L}$ where, $\text{L} = (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}$, $(\text{n-C}_3\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$, $(\text{n-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{S}$, $(\text{n-C}_5\text{H}_{11})_2\text{S}$, $(\text{n-C}_6\text{H}_{13})_2\text{S}$, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{S}$ and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SCH} : \text{CH}$. The complexes are non-electrolytes and monomeric in dilute solutions. The ^1H nmr and the ir data of the complexes are discussed.

A number of complexes of CrO_2Cl_2 with phosphorus halides¹, amides², titanium tetrachloride³ and nitrogen bases^{4,5} have been reported. Complexes of CrO_2Cl_2 with sulphur ligands have not been prepared. As a part of our study on hydrodeheterogenation of model compounds found in coal utilising metal complexes of the heteroatom species, we have prepared and characterised complexes of sulphur ligands found in coal, with CrO_2Cl_2 . The ligands used are R_2S ($\text{R} = \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$, $\text{n-C}_3\text{H}_7$, $\text{n-C}_4\text{H}_9$, $\text{n-C}_5\text{H}_{11}$, $\text{n-C}_6\text{H}_{13}$), thiophene and benzo[b]thiophene. These are found in coal tar which is recovered from coal on gasification^{6,7}.

Experimental

Dialkyl sulphides (R_2S ; $\text{R} = \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$, $\text{n-C}_3\text{H}_7$, $\text{n-C}_4\text{H}_9$, $\text{n-C}_5\text{H}_{11}$ and $\text{n-C}_6\text{H}_{13}$) were prepared by literature methods⁸. Purity of the ligands was checked by recording their ^1H nmr in CCl_4 (Ref. 9). Thiophene and benzo[b]thiophene (E. Merck) were used as such. Chromium(VI) dioxydichloride was prepared by the reported method¹⁰, and repeatedly distilled; fraction distilling at $117^\circ/740$ mm was collected for use. Carbon tetrachloride, dimethyl

sulphoxide, nitromethane, nitrobenzene and diethyl ether were purified and dried before use.

Preparation of complexes: In a typical preparation, to an ice-cold solution of a known weight (25-30 mmol) of the base in dry CCl_4 (~50 ml) was added dropwise a stoichiometric amount of an ice-cold solution of CrO_2Cl_2 in CCl_4 . The contents were magnetically stirred for ~2 h; the reaction was exothermic. In case of thiophene and benzo[b]thiophene, fine powdered solids were formed, but in case of dialkyl sulphides, solid sticky mass was obtained, which on trituration with dry ether gave fine powder. The isolated complexes were filtered under dry N_2 , washed repeatedly with dry diethyl ether and finally dried under vacuum.

Analytical methods: Chromium in the complexes was estimated by heating them to $900-1000^\circ$ and weighing the residue as Cr_2O_3 . Chlorine was estimated by Volhard's method. Sulphur was estimated as BaSO_4 after fusing the known weight of the complex with fusion mixture (Na_2O_2 and Na_2CO_3 in 1 : 2 ratio). Analytical data and colour of the complexes are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES OF CHROMIUM(VI) DIOXYDICHLORIDE

Compd.*	Colour	M.p. °C	Molecular weight		Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
			Concn. $\times 10^2 M$	Found/ (Calcd.)	Cr	Cl	S
$\text{A} \cdot 2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}$	Blackish brown	80	4.182 0	317.15 (335.4)	15.01 (15.50)	21.02 (21.17)	19.00 (19.08)
$\text{A} \cdot 2(\text{n-C}_3\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$	Dark brown	85	2.295 2	389.05 (391.48)	12.82 (13.28)	18.04 (18.13)	16.23 (16.34)
$\text{A} \cdot 2(\text{n-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{S}$	Dark brown	92	7.344 5	443.99 (447.60)	10.85 (11.61)	15.66 (15.86)	13.91 (14.39)
$\text{A} \cdot 2(\text{n-C}_5\text{H}_{11})_2\text{S}$	Dark brown	107	6.961 6	492.129 (503.70)	9.62 (10.32)	13.62 (14.09)	12.31 (12.70)
$\text{A} \cdot 2(\text{n-C}_6\text{H}_{13})_2\text{S}$	Dark violet	119	2.580 0	553.40 (559.82)	9.07 (9.28)	12.31 (12.68)	11.28 (11.43)
$\text{A} \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{S}$	Black	>300	2.714 7	39.64 (323.28)	15.72 (16.08)	20.92 (21.96)	19.57 (19.79)
$\text{A} \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SCH} : \text{CH}$	Deep grey	>300	0.135 0	15.83 (423.40)	11.98 (12.28)	15.92 (16.76)	14.89 (15.11)

* $\text{A} = \text{CrO}_2\text{Cl}_2$.

Physical measurements : The ir spectra of the complexes were recorded in nujol and hexachlorobutadiene between KBr plates using a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer in the range 4 000-400 cm^{-1} . The ^1H nmr spectra of the ligands and their complexes were recorded on a Varian EM 390 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as external reference. Molecular weight of the complexes was determined in dimethyl sulphoxide solution cryoscopically. The molar conductance of millimolar solutions in dimethyl sulphoxide and nitromethane was determined at 25° using Toshniwal CLOI/02A conductivity bridge and dip type conductance cell with a cell constant of 0.521 cm^{-1} . Thermal analysis was carried out in an atmosphere of air by means of MOM Budapest Derivatograph (Type : Paulik, Paulik and Erdey) containing Pt-Rh thermocouples.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are moisture-sensitive solids except $\text{CrO}_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{S}$ and $\text{CrO}_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{SCH} : \text{CH}$. The complexes are insoluble in common non-polar organic solvents but dissolve in dimethyl sulphoxide, nitrobenzene, nitromethane, chloroform and dichloromethane except $\text{CrO}_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{SCH} : \text{CH}$ which is soluble only in dimethyl sulphoxide and dimethyl formamide.

The analytical results (Table 1) show that the complexes of CrO_2Cl_2 with sulphur ligands have 1 : 2 stoichiometry. The molecular weights of the complexes (Table 1) in dimethyl sulphoxide correspond very nearly to the monomeric formula weight in very dilute solutions but a considerable decrease in molecular weights of the complexes at higher concentration can be attributed to their association. Molecular weights of $\text{CrO}_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{S}$ and $\text{CrO}_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{SCH} : \text{CH}$ found very low even at very low concentration, indicate their associative nature in dimethyl sulphoxide. The molar conductance values of the millimolar solutions of these complexes in various solvents (DMSO, 8-18 ; MeNO_2 , 2-7 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) reveal their non-electrolytic nature.

Infrared study : The ir spectra of the complexes along with tentative assignment are presented in Table 2. $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ have been assigned as discussed by earlier workers¹¹⁻¹³. However, their interpretation in $\text{CrO}_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{R}_2\text{S}$ (R = ethyl, n-propyl, n-butyl, n-pentyl and n-hexyl) is not straight forward, owing to the occurrence of different rotational isomers of the ligands. In these complexes, the bands at 1 240 and 785-790 cm^{-1} are attributed to CH_2 wagging and rocking modes, respectively for *gauche* conformation, other vibrations attributed to CH_2 *trans* form. This may indicate that complexes consist of mixtures of *trans* and *gauche* isomers,

TABLE 2—IR SPECTRAL DATA* OF COMPLEXES OF CHROMIUM(VI) DIOXYDICHLORIDE** WITH TENTATIVE ASSIGNMENTS

A.2L ₁	A.2L ₂	A.2L ₃	A.2L ₄	A.2L ₅	A.2C ₄ H ₉ S	A.2C ₆ H ₅ SCH : OH	Assignment
2 940sb	2 960sb	2 975sb	2 960sb	2 940sb	2 960sb	2 980sb	$\nu_{\text{asym}} (\text{C-H})$
2 880m	2 890m	2 890w	2 880m	2 880m	2 880w	2 880w	$\nu_{\text{sym}} (\text{C-H})$
					1 600s	1 625s	$\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$
1 460s	1 460vs	1 470s	1 470s	1 465s	1 460vs	1 465vs	$\delta_{\text{asym}} (\text{C-H})$
1 370s	1 380s	1 390s	1 385m	1 385m	1 380s	1 380vs	$\delta_{\text{sym}} (\text{C-H})$
1 240 w	1 240m	1 240w	1 240w	1 240w			$\rho_w (\text{CH}_2 \text{ gauche})$
					1 240w	1 260w	$\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}} + \nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$
					1 225w	1 210w	$\rho_w (\text{CH})$
					1 170w	1 170w	
1 155wb	1 160m	1 165w	1 165wb	1 165wb			$\rho_w (\text{CH}_2 \text{ trans})$
1 070m	1 065wb	1 080w	1 090w	1 090w			$\rho_t (\text{CH}_2 \text{ trans})$
930sb	930sb	940sb	935sb	930sb			$\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}} + \rho_t (\text{CH}_2)$
					935vs	935vs	$\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$
785w	785s	790w	785w	790w			$\rho_r (\text{CH}_2 \text{ gauche})$
					780m	785s	$\rho_r (\text{OH})$
720s	720m	720s	725s	725s			$\nu_{\text{C-S}} + \rho_r (\text{CH}_2 \text{ gauche})$
					720w	725w	$\nu_{\text{C-S}} + \rho_r (\text{OH})$
500sb	500sb	520sb	525sb	525sb	535s	535s	$\nu_{\text{C}-\text{S}}$
440w	440w	450w	450w	430w	440w	435w	$\nu_{\text{C}-\text{Cl}}$

* s=strong, b=broad, w=weak, m=medium, v=very.

** A = CrO_2Cl_2 ; L₁ = $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}$, L₂ = $(\text{n-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{S}$, L₃ = $(\text{n-C}_6\text{H}_{13})_2\text{S}$, L₄ = $(\text{n-C}_8\text{H}_{17})_2\text{S}$ and L₅ = $(\text{n-C}_{10}\text{H}_{21})_2\text{S}$.

TABLE 3—¹H NMR SPECTRA OF LIGANDS AND COMPLEXES

Ligand	Chemical shift (δppm)			Complex*	Chemical shift (δppm)		
	H _a	H _b	H _c		H _a	H _b	H _c
(^a OH, ^b CH ₂) ₂ S	1.86	2.69	—	A.2(^a CH ₂ , ^b OH) ₂ S	1.40	3.00	—
(^a OH, ^c CH ₂ , ^b CH ₂) ₂ S	1.06	2.56	1.66	A.2(^a CH ₂ , ^c CH ₂ , ^b CH ₂) ₂ S	1.09	2.86	1.69
(^a OH, ^c (CH ₂) ₂ , ^b CH ₂) ₂ S	0.96	2.56	1.56	A.2(^a OH, ^c (CH ₂) ₂ , ^b CH ₂) ₂ S	0.99	2.86	1.59
(^a CH ₂ , ^c (CH ₂) ₂ , ^b CH ₂) ₂ S	0.96	2.56	1.46	A.2(^a CH ₂ , ^c (CH ₂) ₂ , ^b CH ₂) ₂ S	0.96	2.84	1.49
(^a CH ₂ , ^c CH ₂ , ^b CH ₂) ₂ S	0.90	2.46	1.33	A.2(^a CH ₂ , ^c CH ₂ , ^b CH ₂) ₂ S	0.90	2.74	1.36
)	7.33	7.81	—				
)	8.03	8.41	7.76				

* A=CrO₂Cl₂.

differing only in configuration of the ligand. Bands at 1 240 cm⁻¹ in CrO₂Cl₂.2C₄H₄S and 1 260 cm⁻¹ in CrO₂Cl₂.2C₆H₄SCH : CH have been assigned to ν_{C-S}+ν_{C=C} which appears in the range 1 270-1 200 cm⁻¹ (Ref. 13). In pure chromium(VI) dioxidichloride ν_{Cr=O} and ν_{Cr-Cl} appear at 984 and 465 cm⁻¹, respectively^{14,15}. The most predominant feature in the ir spectra of all the complexes is a very sharp and broad band in the region 930-940 cm⁻¹ and a weak band in the region 430-450 cm⁻¹ assigned to ν_{Cr=O} and ν_{Cr-Cl}, respectively. Broadening of ν_{Cr=O} band is due to appearance of CH₂ rocking vibration in the same region. Another important feature of the spectra of the complexes is the presence of ν_{C-S} which appears in the complexes in the region 720-725 cm⁻¹. This is slightly lower in position relative to the ν_{C-S} in free ligands (735 cm⁻¹) Ref. 12). These shifts to lower region indicate the formation of Cr-S bond in the complexes, appearing in the region 500-535 cm⁻¹.

¹H nmr study: ¹H nmr spectra of dialkyl sulphides and their complexes were recorded in CDCl₃ solution, while those of thiophene, benzo[b]-thiophene and their complexes in DMSO solution. Proton chemical shifts of the ligands and their complexes are shown in Table 3. H_b protons in the complexes appear at δ 0.20-0.31 down-field as compared to H_b protons in pure ligands. Coordination by the ligands reduce the electron density around C_b, resulting in its deshielding relative to the uncomplexed ligands, causing H_b protons to undergo resonance at a lower applied magnetic

field. Other signals of the protons do not differ much from those of the corresponding ligands.

Thermal study: Thermal decomposition of the complexes has been studied upto 900°. Detachment of the ligands from the complexes should be an endothermic process, however, TG and DTG curves show that decomposition takes place exothermally in three steps. This may be due to the fact that the thermal decomposition being studied in an atmosphere of air and the ligand that is removed from the complex gets decomposed by air exothermally, and this exothermic step overpower the endothermic step which is recorded by the derivatograph. DTG minima (Fig. 1) have been projected on TG curves to get inflection points (marked by small arrows on TG curves). Complexes start decomposing around 90°. In the range 440-515°, Cr₂O₃ residue is formed which has been analysed. Experimental and theoretical losses in each step agree well. The intermediates were not characterised. General mode of decomposition may be represented as

where, L=ligand molecule.

Fig. 1. TG curves of complexes : (O) $\text{CrO}_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2(\text{n-C}_6\text{H}_7)_2\text{S}$ (A), ($\square$) $\text{CrO}_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2(\text{n-C}_8\text{H}_{11})_2\text{S}$ (B), and (Δ) $\text{CrO}_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2(\text{C}_4\text{H}_8)_2\text{S}$ (C).

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